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THE EVOLUTION OF TRANSLATION STUDIES: KEY FIGURES AND CONCEPTS

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Abstract: This article examines translation, tracing its history, highlighting key figures in translation studies, focusing on contributions of Uzbek scholars, and exploring various aspects and methods of the translation process.

Keywords: translation, style, translation studies, Uzbek literature, original text, lexical equivalents, culture, figurative language, scholars

ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ ПЕРЕВОДОВЕДЕНИЯ: КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ ФИГУРЫ И КОНЦЕПЦИИ

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Аннотация: В этой статье рассматривается перевод, прослеживается его история, выделяются ключевые фигуры в переводоведении, уделяется внимание вкладу узбекских ученых и изучаются различные аспекты и методы процесса перевода.

Ключевые слова: перевод, стиль, переводоведение, узбекская литература, оригинальный текст, лексические эквиваленты, культура, образный язык, ученые

Translation is vital for building understanding and interest between different cultures and peoples. The first theoretical discussions about translation appeared in ancient Rome. Aristotle, Cicero, and Horace believed that translators should carefully weigh the meaning before translating it. Translation studies as a distinct field developed significantly thanks to the contributions of renowned linguists and scholars such as V. Komissarov, A. Fedorov, L. Barkhudarov, Ya. Retker, G'. Salomov, Q. Musayev, Yu. Nayda, J. Catford, and others. Notable works include N. K. Garbovsky's "Theory of Translation" (2004) and S. B. Veledinskaya's "Course on General Translation Theory" (2010). Theory of translation didn't really take shape until the 1920s, when translation studies emerged as a field of academic study. Since then, the field has continued to grow, with numerous scholarly works, textbooks, and manuals being published on

various aspects of translation. Early examples of outstanding literary translation in Uzbek literature include the works of Hamza Hakimzoda Niyoziy, Abdulla Qodiriy, Chulpon, Hamid Olimjon, G'afur G'ulom, Abdulla Qahhor, Oybek, Mirtemir and many others. Moreover, M. Royiq and S. Siddiq were early pioneers in translation practice, even developing some of the first Uzbek translation theory guides. G'. Salomov later established a significant school of translation studies, contributing extensively to the field, especially in the area of idiom translation. Other important figures in Uzbek translation include I. G'afurov, O. Mo'minov, N. Qambarov, and K. Jo'rayev. Currently, the research of G. Boqieva and A. Abduazizov on translation is highly regarded.

Since the independence of Uzbekistan, there's been a significant increase in focus on translation. Efforts have been made to promote the Uzbek language, translate foreign literature and academic works into Uzbek, and enrich linguistic and cultural diversity. Simultaneously, translating Uzbek literature into other languages has fostered cultural exchange and enhanced Uzbekistan's international standing. Advances in translation technology and online platforms have also facilitated the wider dissemination of translated works. Furthermore, growing international interest in Uzbek literature, art, and culture has increased the demand for translations of Uzbek literary works into foreign languages, further stimulating translation activity in the country. With the rapid growth of international relations today, the volume of documents requiring translation is constantly increasing. In recent years, there's been a significant rise in both spoken and written translation, along with a substantial increase in the number of people working as translators.

While translation might seem straightforward, it's actually quite complex. The use of figurative language demands skill and precision from the translator to avoid misinterpretations. Idiomatic expressions, in particular, are very delicate to translate, as their meaning isn't simply the sum of the individual words. Therefore, careful consideration is necessary. Furthermore, the differences in grammatical structure and cultural context between languages like Uzbek and English, which belong to entirely different language families, present additional significant challenges. A good translation conveys the author's meaning so effectively that the reader feels they are reading the original text in its original language. In other words, a translation is truly successful only when the reader is unaware that they are reading a translation. The style of the original text is crucial to a successful translation; style and stylistics are indispensable. This is because style is one of the most difficult aspects of translation, often hindering a complete understanding of the meaning. Style is the specific form that embodies the author's voice, the

genre, and the literary or artistic expression of the work. The word "style" itself precisely means the way language is used by a specific person, in a specific context, and for a specific purpose.

Furthermore, another challenge in translation is finding lexical equivalents for objects or events. A translator must understand not only two languages but also two cultures. Due to differences between languages and cultures, lexical equivalents may not exist. This can be caused by geographical variations, customs, beliefs, worldviews, and other factors. To accurately convey the meaning, the translator must find new ways and methods. Here are some translation methods which include: keeping the translation unchanged; partially modifying the translation; replacing the translation with a completely different image; or omitting the translation entirely.

In short, although translators utilize their own creative approaches and techniques, they must always prioritize accurately representing the author's original ideas and subjective viewpoints.

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